
The Effect of Brand Awareness, Brand Image, and Instagram on Purchase Decisions

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of brand awareness, brand image, and Instagram on consumer purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. Researchers used the sample used in this study as many as 105 respondents who came from consumers who were consumers of Bittersweet by Najla snacks. To analyze data validation, researchers used the analysis technique adopted in this study used validity test using Pearson Correlation, and reliability test using Cronchbach's Alpha, multiple linear regression, t test, and coefficient of determination. The results showed that: (1) there is a positive and significant influence between brand awareness on purchasing decisions with a significant value of $0.035 < 0.05$; (2) there is an influence between brand image and purchasing decisions with a significant value of $0.006 < 0.05$; (3) there is a significant influence between Instagram on purchasing decisions with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$; and (4) the results of the test for the coefficient of determination show an adjusted R square value of 0.574 which means that as much as 57.4% of the dependent variable in purchasing decisions there are independent variables, namely brand awareness, brand image, and Instagram. While other factors 42.6% are influenced by other factors not examined.

KEYWORDS: Ringan Brand Awareness, Brand Image, Instagram, Purchase Decision

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumer purchasing decisions on a product do not just happen, but require several processes. The definition of purchasing decisions according to Kotler, & Keller (2016) is as follows: Consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations select, buy, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and wants. which can be interpreted Purchasing decisions are part of consumer behavior consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations select, buy, use, and how goods, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy their needs and wants. One of the important roles in marketing is the brand. There is a big difference between product and brand. Products are made by factories, but brands are bought by consumers. If a product can be easily imitated by competitors, then the brand will always have a uniqueness that is relatively difficult to imitate. According to Kotler, & Keller (2016) a trademark is a name, term, symbol, symbol or design intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and differentiate them from other competitors, or a combination thereof..

Brand awareness is a consumer's ability to identify a brand under different conditions, this can be done by brand recognition and recall of a particular brand. There is also another notion of brand awareness, namely the individual's ability to recognize and remember the brand of a certain type of product, and is the main dimension of brand equity according to Kotler, and Armstrong, (2014). Sihombing, (2019) Consumers also pay attention to the image of a brand (brand image) in making a purchase decision.

Associations or consumer perceptions based on one's memory of a product can be the definition of brand image or brand image. There is also another sense of brand image, which is not contained in the features, technology or type of product itself, the image arises because of advertising, promotion or users. Wijaya, (2013) suggests brand image also related to how consumers as a target audience of communication interpret (decode) brand messages and actualize it in their life and become part of how they construct their self-concepts and reality. Brand image (Brand Image) is the observation and belief held by consumers, as reflected in associations or in consumers' memories.

A name, term, sign, symbol, design, or a combination of these things, which is intended to identify the goods or services of a person or group of sellers and to differentiate them from competitors' goods and services, the meaning of a brand image according to Kotler, and Keller (2021) Brand image can also be interpreted as a public perception of the company or its products. Image is influenced by many factors beyond the company's control. There are three things that an effective image will influence, namely: first, convincing the product character and value proposition. Second, notify the character in a different way so that it is not confused

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with a competitor's character. Third, providing emotional power that goes beyond mental images, for it to function, images must be conveyed through every available means of communication and brand contact.

Internet users in Indonesia reach 91% in the age group 15-19 years, followed by 88.5% in the age group 20-24 years, 82.7% in the age group 25-29 years, 76.5% in the age group 30-34 years, and the age group 35-39 years of 68.5%. Internet users in Indonesia reached 171,176,716 in 2018, an increase of 27,916,716 compared to 2017. As many as 24.7% use the internet to communicate via news and 18.9% use social media such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube. (APJII, 2018). More than half of Internet users for communication purposes in Indonesia are between 19 and 34 years old (49.52%). These users, commonly referred to as Generation Y and Z, have relied heavily on the digital world since birth and are used to gathering diverse opinions and influencing audiences (Nurhandayani et al., 2019).

Of the various types of communication media above, only a few are the favorite communication media in Indonesia. The favorite social media in Indonesia are Facebook, Whatsapp, LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram. However, according to the agency's analysis, Afwan, & Santosa, (2020). Instagram is the most effective social media platform for boosting business. Instagram is a mobile online service that can share photos, share videos. In the beginning, Instagram content uploaded by users was only photos and videos of personal moments, but with the advancement of the times and bright ideas, Instagram is used by users to market the products, services, tourism they offer or sell.

Research on brand awareness, brand image, and Instagram (social media) was previously conducted by Aaker (2018) who argued that the results obtained influenced perceptions of product quality, brand image and Instagram advertising media on purchasing decisions for ninebox products. Brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions because of the many similar products, consumers will prefer those that have the best quality according to the buyer's perception. Therefore, at this time many business people have begun to build a perception of product quality with better quality compared to other similar products. Brand image is the consumer's perception of the brand based on consumer memory of the product as a result of what a person feels about the brand in making a product purchase decision, so that it has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. Instagram has a positive and significant influence on buyer decisions because Instagram is a photo-sharing application that allows users to take photos, apply digital filters, and share them with various social networking services, including Instagram's own.

In addition, research Malonda, Lopian, & Mandagie, (2018). states that the effect of brand image on purchasing decisions, through hypothesis testing shows a positive but not significant effect. In this study, brand image is not important and does not influence purchasing decisions. Because the Manado IT Center is expected to be able to maintain existing quality on an ongoing basis, especially to retain consumers. It is expected that the Manado IT Center can apply the right strategy to generate ideas and ideas in competition. The selection is based on the observation that the buyer's decision affects brand awareness, brand image, and Instagram has an effect on attracting consumer attention.

Through the existing research gap, further research is carried out on the Influence of Brand Awareness, Brand Image, and Instagram on Purchasing Decisions

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Every individual must have a different perspective, and that perspective influences consumer choices define purchasing decisions as consumer decisions to buy or not to buy. Basically there are two determining factors that influence consumer purchasing decisions, namely environmental strengths and individual factors Dharmmesta, et. al. (2017).

Aaker (2018) defines brand awareness as the ability of potential buyers to recognize or remember a brand as part of a certain product category. According to Kartajaya (2010 in Putri and Atmosphere 2018), defines a brand as an asset that creates value for customers by increasing satisfaction and appreciating quality. According to Duriyanto, et al (2017: 54) Brand awareness is the ability of a potential buyer to recognize or recall a brand as part of a certain product category. People tend to like or buy familiar brands because they feel safe with something they know. According to Husnawati (2017) Brand awareness is one of the basic dimensions of a brand's equity which is often considered as one of the requirements of a consumer's purchasing decision, because it is an important factor in considering a brand.

Brand image according to Kotler and Keller (2016) is the consumer's perception of a brand as a reflection of the associations that exist in consumers' minds. According to Kottler and Keller (2017) that brand image consists of components: Attributes (Product related attributes, Non-product related attributes), Benefits (Functional benefits, Experiential benefits, Symbolic benefits), Brand Attitude

According to Febiyan (2015) added Instagram is one of the most popular social media in the world, including Indonesia, which has millions of members from various types of social media accounts. In line with that, Rohmadi (2016) explained Instagram in terms of function. Rohmadi (2016) explains that for those of you who have difficulty writing, Instagram can be an alternative for sharing and self-existence.

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Figure. 1 Theoretical Framework

The formulation of the hypothesis in this study is:

Previous research by Najib, Muhammad Alfiyan and Soesanto, Harry and Sukresna, I Made (2016)) shows that brand awareness has a positive effect on purchasing decisions

H1 : Brand awareness influences the buyer's decision.

Previous research by Syafirah, et. al., 2017 shows that Brand Image influences the decision to purchase vans products

H2: Brand Image influences the buyer's decision.

Previous research by Aaker (2018) shows that the influence of Instagram Advertising Media, and Perceived Quality on Purchase Decisions of Vans Products

H3: Instagram influences the buyer's decision

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Descriptive quantitative method is selected as research design which capable to evaluate all hypotheses results as well as describe the correlation between variables (ferry enrichment). Quantitative research methods are research methods that adhere to the principle of positivism by examining certain populations or samples using research instruments aimed at testing predetermined hypotheses (endah enrichment). The results of the data collection will be processed using the SPSS application to produce statistical data processing. The population in this study was konsumen produk Bittersweet by Najla. The saturated sample technique was chosen for use in this study because the population was limited to only 105 respondents.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure. 2 Data Normality Test Results
Source: Data processed by SPSS (2022)

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From Figure 2 above it can be seen that the dots spread around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line. So it can be concluded that the data in this study were normally distributed.

Table. 1 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	Brand Awareness	.362	2.760
	Brand Image	.322	3.110
	Instagram	.563	1.777

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian
Source: Data processed by SPSS (2022)

Based on table 1, the VIF value for the independent variables brand awareness, brand image and Instagram has a value less than 10 and has a tolerance value (TOL) of not less than 0.1. Based on these results, it was concluded that the three independent variables used did not experience multicollinearity problems.

Multiple linear regression analysis was carried out to determine the relationship between brand awareness, brand image and Instagram independent variables on purchasing decisions for Bittersweet by Najla products and will be analyzed using multiple regression analysis with a level of 0.05 or 5%. The results of the regression in the study can be seen in the following 4.16 regression table.

Table. 2 Multiple Linear Regression

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.107	1.339		2.321	.022
	Brand Awareness	.271	.127	.227	2.135	.035
	Brand Image	.290	.104	.314	2.782	.006
	Instagram	.345	.091	.323	3.791	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian
Source: Data processed by SPSS (2022)

Based on the regression results in table 2, the multiple linear regression equation model can be formulated as follows:

$$\hat{Y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$$

$$\hat{Y} = 3,107 + 0,271 X_1 + 0,290 X_2 + 0,345 X_3$$

The above equation means that:

1. The constant a of 3.107 indicates that, if brand awareness, brand image and Instagram are 0 (no change), then the purchase decision has a value of 3.107.
2. Brand awareness variable regression coefficient of 0.271 indicates a positive direction. This means that the brand awareness variable has a smaller influence on purchasing decisions.
3. The regression coefficient of the brand image variable is 0.290 indicating a positive direction. This means that the brand image variable has a greater influence than the brand awareness variable on purchasing decisions
4. The regression coefficient of the instagram variable is 0.345 indicating a positive direction. This means that the Instagram variable has the greatest influence on purchasing decisions

From the results of the regression analysis above, it can be concluded that the regression model is feasible to use to predict the independent variables (brand awareness, brand image and Instagram) on the dependent variable (purchasing decision).

Table. 3 Test Results F

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1136.807	3	378.936	47.710	.000 ^b
	Residual	802.183	101	7.942		
	Total	1938.990	104			

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian
b. Predictors: (Constant), Instagram, Kesadaran Merek, Citra Merek
Source: Data processed by SPSS (2022)

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The test results in table 3 show that the sig. F (Statistic) of 0.000 is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 and the F statistic value > from F table is 447.710 > 2.69. This means that brand awareness, brand image and Instagram simultaneously influence purchasing decisions

Table. 4 Partial t test

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.107	1.339		2.321	.022
	Brand Awareness	.271	.127	.227	2.135	.035
	Brand Image	.290	.104	.314	2.782	.006
	Instagram	.345	.091	.323	3.791	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian

Source: Data processed by SPSS (2022)

Based on the results of the t test above, then:

1. Based on table 4 it is known that the sig. brand awareness variable <critical probability value ($\alpha = 5\%$) of 0.035 < 0.05 and tcount > ttable of 2.135 > 1.98. This means that brand awareness influences purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. Based on these statistical results, the conclusion of the study is to accept hypothesis 1.
2. Based on table 4, it is known that the sig. brand image variable <critical probability value ($\alpha = 5\%$) of 0.006 < 0.05 and tcount > ttable of 2.782 > 1.98. This means that brand image influences purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. Based on these statistical results, the conclusion of the study is to accept hypothesis 2.
3. Based on table 4, it is known that the sig. instagram variable <critical probability value ($\alpha = 5\%$) of 0.000 < 0.05 and tcount > ttable of 3.791 > 1.98. This means that Instagram is influential terhadap keputusan pembelian pada produk Bittersweet by Najla. Berdasarkan hasil statistik tersebut, maka kesimpulan pada penelitian adalah menerima hipotesis 3.

Tabel. 5 Koefisien Determinasi (R²)

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.766 ^a	.586	.574	2.818	1.854

a. Predictors: (Constant), Instagram, Kesadaran Merek, Citra Merek

b. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian

Source: Data processed by SPSS (2022)

The results of the coefficient of determination in table 5 show that the value of the coefficient of determination is 0.586. This study uses three independent variables, so the adjusted r square value is used to measure the proportion of the independent variable's influence on the dependent variable. The adjusted r square coefficient of 0.574 indicates that the proportion of the influence of the independent variables brand awareness, brand image and Instagram on purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products is 57.4 percent while the remaining 42.6 percent (100 – 57.4 percent) is influenced by variables others that were not examined in the study.

The influence of brand awareness on purchasing decisions

Based on the results of the partial significant test that has been carried out, it is known that the sig. brand awareness <critical probability value ($\alpha = 5\%$) of 0.035 < 0.05 and the tcount > ttable is 2.135 > 1.98, so that brand awareness influences purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. Based on these statistical results, the first hypothesis proposed by the author can be accepted. The brand awareness regression coefficient shows a positive direction. This means that brand awareness has a positive influence on purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products, where the better brand awareness, the purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products will increase.

According to Aaker (2018) brand awareness is the ability of a potential buyer to recognize or recall a brand as part of a particular product category. Every marketing activity always strives to obtain a higher level of brand awareness as top of mind. If a brand is not in the minds of consumers, the brand is not considered in the minds of consumers.

This research is in line with research conducted by Pramana, Billi Wicahya Rendra (2020) with the title "The Influence of Social Media Marketing on Brand Awareness and Brand Image that Impacts Purchase Decisions for Batik Keris Products" which shows that brand awareness has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decisions.

Effect of brand image on purchasing decisions

Based on the results of the partial significant test that has been carried out, it is known that the sig. brand image <critical probability value ($\alpha = 5\%$) of 0.006 < 0.05 and the tcount > ttable is 2.782 > 1.98, so that brand image influences purchasing decisions on

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Bittersweet by Najla products. Based on these statistical results, the second hypothesis proposed by the author can be accepted. The brand image regression coefficient shows a positive direction. This means that brand image has a positive relationship to purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products, where the better the brand image, the purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products will increase.

According to Kotler and Keller (2016) Brand image is the consumer's perception of a brand as a reflection of the associations that exist in consumers' minds. Regina Virvilaite et al (2015) stated that brand image is the content of the product because when consumers buy a product, they buy an image that is formed during feedback.

This research is in line with research conducted by Pramana, Billi Wicahya Rendra (2020) with the title "The Influence of Social Media Marketing on Brand Awareness and Brand Image that Impacts Purchase Decisions for Batik Keris Products" which shows that brand image has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decisions.

The influence of Instagram on purchasing decisions

Based on the results of the partial significant test that has been carried out, it is known that the sig. instagram <critical probability value ($\alpha = 5\%$) of 0.000 <0.05 and the tcount > ttable is 3.791 > 1.98, so that instagram influences purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. Based on these statistical results, the third hypothesis proposed by the author can be accepted. Instagram regression coefficient shows a positive direction. This means that Instagram has a positive relationship to purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products, where the better the Instagram, the purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products will increase.

According to Febiyan (2015) Instagram is a social media that allows its users to upload or share photos and videos which can be edited to make it more attractive with various filters via a smartphone.

This research is in line with research conducted by Tyas & Hutagaol, 2021 entitled "The Effect of Social Media Content on Buying Decisions of HijUp.com" which shows that there is a positive influence between Facebook social media content and Instagram social media content simultaneously on purchasing decisions HijUp.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aims to determine whether brand awareness, brand image and Instagram simultaneously influence purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out, the following conclusions are obtained:

1. Based on the results of the study, it is known that brand awareness has the least influence on purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products and is significant. This means that the better the brand awareness that Bittersweet by Najla consumers do, the purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products will increase.
2. Based on the research results, it is known that the brand image variable has a greater influence than the brand awareness variable on purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. This means that the better the brand image of Bittersweet by Najla consumers, the purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products will increase.
3. Based on the research results, it is known that the Instagram variable has the greatest influence on purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. This means that the better and more interesting the Instagram Bittersweet is, the purchasing decision on Bittersweet by Najla products will increase.
4. The results of the research conducted show that brand awareness, brand image and Instagram influence purchasing decisions on Bittersweet by Najla products. The proportion of influence that is brand awareness, brand image and Instagram is 57.4 percent while the remaining 42.6 percent is influenced by other variables not examined in the study

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